

Landform-regolith Map of the Central Goren Greenstone Belt, Burkina Faso

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2024
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Scale: 1:20 000
 Contour interval: 1m
 Projection: WGS 84 / UTM Zone 30N

The map is based on extensive fieldwork and complementary photo-interpretation. Field mapping was undertaken at 1:10 000 scale on the basis of a Lidar digital elevation model converted into topographic sheets with 1-m contours. Coverage of the study area required 60 days of fieldwork during the years 2017 and 2018. Around 300 km of itinerary was covered on foot. Geomorphological observations, regolith description and sampling were carried out at more than 700 stations. Twenty landform-regolith association units were defined, which are of four types: (i) landform-regolith associations of Paleogene Etchplain, (ii) landform-regolith associations of Neogene Pediment/Glaciis systems, (iii) landform-regolith associations of erosional terrains, (iv) landform-regolith associations of the active pediplain. A summary of the identification criteria of the map units and their potential use for economic geology purpose are provided in Sawadogo et al. (2020).

CITE THE MAP AS
 SAWADOGO, B., CHARDON, D., & BAMBA, O. (2024). Landform-regolith Map of the Central Goren Greenstone Belt, Burkina Faso. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10600761>

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS
 Benjamin Sawadogo: Field mapping, photo-interpretation, conceptualization, methodology, GIS implementation
 Dominique Chardon: Conceptualization, methodology, supervision
 Ousmane Bamba: Conceptualization, methodology

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS
 This map was produced as part of the first author's PhD project, which was supported by the IRD (JEA1 FasoLith). We thank NordGold for providing the contour map.

DESCRIPTION OF LANDFORM-REGOLITH ASSOCIATIONS

1. Paleogene Etchplain

Bauxitic Mantled Etchplain

1Bx Duricrust-capped Bauxitic Mantled Etchplain (i.e. the "African Surface"). It is an indurated bauxite or - more rarely - an AlFe duricrust covering the surface (50-100 m) and oldest weathering profile that once covered the entire sub region. Weathering of the mantled etchplain started at least in the Late Cretaceous and ultimate duricrusting in the Mid-Eocene (55 - 45 Ma; Beauvais and Chardon, 2013; Chardon, 2023). This map unit is preserved as mesas that rise to heights of 100-150 m above the regional plan. Geomorphology of the etchplain relics suggests that the bauxite landscape had a typical wavelength of 3-5 km and a relief of 50-40 m.

2Hx Duricrust-capped Intermediate Mantled Etchplain. The etchplain developed after dissection of the Bauxitic Mantled Etchplain (~45 Ma) and underwent weathering and duricrusting until the end-Oligocene (20-24 Ma; Beauvais and Chardon, 2013). It formed wide (5 km) valleys under relics of the Bauxitic Mantled Etchplain. The Intermediate Mantled Etchplain is capped by a thick (2-10 m) nodular, pisolitic or massive ferricrete that derives from weathering of the underlying bedrock or consists of detrital material. The underlying regolith is partly inherited from the bauxitic period of weathering and consists of detrital material. The underlying regolith is partly inherited from the bauxitic period of weathering. The comprehensive weathering profile commonly attains 50 m thickness. Relics of the Intermediate Mantled Etchplain are of 2 types: (i) radiating ridges sloping from under bauxitic mesas that are shaded with micro-scale blocks of Al-Fe duricrust (e.g. Rabaska massif) and (ii) isolated, distal plateaus sloping from bauxitic mesas that are capped by a massive ferricrete (e.g. plateaus near Tampongas massif).

2HxG Intermediate Mantled Etchplain devoid of its duricrust capping horizon. The duricrust has been stripped off so that the underlying Fe-carapace horizon remains, whereas the overall landform of the Intermediate Mantled Etchplain is preserved. The Fe-carapace is 2 to 10 m thick. It is typically reddish or dark red and friable. It consists of duricrust pisolitic concretions (1-30 cm in size) cemented by an ochre-orange matrix made of gravels and sands of Fe-oxides and a silty to clayey mix of Fe-oxides and clays (reworked saprolite). The Fe-carapace grades downward into a thick (> 30 m) saprolite horizon.

2HxR Residual hills of the Intermediate Mantled Etchplain resulting from erosion and partial duricrusting / collapse of the original Mantled Etchplain (degradation of unit 2Hx). The residual hills are covered with boulders and gravels resulting from the dismantling of the duricrust and carapace. Originally deep weathering horizons of the Intermediate weathering profile (saprolite and/or carapace) crop out on the top and/or on the sides of the residual hills.

2. Neogene Pediment/Glaciis systems

High Glaciis system

3HxG Duricrust High glaciis. The high glaciis system developed during the Early Miocene. It has been weathered and duricrusted mostly between 18 and 11 Ma (Beauvais and Chardon, 2013). These map units are pediment slopes of the topographic masses preserving relics of the upper paleo-landform-regolith associations. They consist of a fine-grained (fine-slope) and very slightly concave plateau capped by a detrital ferricrete made of Fe-oxides clasts and Fe-oxides cemented by Ferruginous. The comprehensive weathering profile does not exceed 20 m in thickness. The ferricretes are 2 to 4 m thick and are of two types: (i) a coarse conglomeratic type, mostly found on the upper slopes of plateaus and on the upper pediments to the topographic masses, and (ii) a fine-grained type (sand-gravel), typically found in the distal part of the plateau and on the lower pediment slopes of the massif.

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3HxR Residual hills of High glaciis. The hills result from erosion, downwasting and collapse of the High glaciis (degradation of unit 3HxG). They are covered with gravels of the High glaciis ferricrete and expose mostly the High glaciis carapace horizon (see 3HxG).

4MxG Duricrusted Middle glaciis. The Middle glaciis system developed in the Late Miocene. It was weathered and duricrusted mostly at the end-Miocene (7-6 Ma; Beauvais and Chardon, 2013). This is the best preserved duricrusted paleo-landform-regolith association which also formed the pediments of the topographic masses. Its capping ferricrete is detrital and has a gravel or sand granitometry. It is more porous and friable (< 2 m) than that of the High glaciis. The underlying weathering profile is thin (< 5 m). Large relics of this landform-regolith association are functional transportation surfaces for sediments during the rainy season (day to September). Middle glaciis relics commonly form a continuous land surface with the High glaciis relics, from which it is distinguished only by a subtle break of slope.

4MxG Middle glaciis devoid of its ferricrete cover. The Fe-carapace cements the glaciis surface whose weathering ferricrete layer has been stripped off. The Fe-carapace of the Middle glaciis is similar to that of the High glaciis (see 3HxG), but Fe concretions are rare and often macroscopically invisible.

4MxR Middle glaciis exposing an Older Fe-carapace. This carapace is often that of the Intermediate Mantled Etchplain (see 2HxG), which has been returned by erosion during the development of the Middle glaciis system. Although exposed on a glaciis surface, the carapace is derived from the weathering of the underlying bedrock.

4MxR Residual hills of the Middle glaciis. The hills result from erosion, downwasting and collapse of the Middle glaciis (degradation of unit 4MxG). They are covered with gravels of the Middle glaciis ferricrete and expose mostly the Middle glaciis carapace horizon (see 4MxG).

Low glaciis system

5LxG Duricrusted Low glaciis. The low glaciis was duricrusted around 3 Ma (2-2.9 Ma; Beauvais et al., 2008). It is part of the functional pediplain. It is found at a few locations where the intermediate overburden of the upper portions of the functional pediplain has been removed, mostly in river cuts (i.e. a thin (< 0.5 m) detrital ferricrete that is weakly cemented (i.e. Fe-carapace).

REFERENCES

Beauvais, A., Chardon, D., 2013. Modes, tempo, and spatial variability of Cenozoic orogenic denudation: the West African example. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 14, 1590-1608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2009.09.025>

Beauvais, A., Ruffet, G., Henricot, O., Colin, F., 2008. Chemical and physical erosion dynamics of the West African Cenozoic morphogenesis: the 39A-40Ar dating of sapropelic Mn oxides. *J. Geophys. Res.*, Earth Surf., 113, E4607. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JE003096>, FO4607.

Chardon, D., Ganiot, J.L., Beauvais, A., Bamba, O., 2018. West African tectonic pediments: Landform-regolith evolution processes and mineral exploration potential. *Earth Sci. Rev.*, 179, 124-146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2018.02.009>

Chardon, D., 2023. Landform-regolith patterns of northwestern Africa: Deciphering Cenozoic surface dynamics of the tropical orogenic geomorphology. *Geomorphology*, 2023, 107622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2023.107622>

Sawadogo, B., Beauvais, A., Chardon, D., 2020. Landform-regolith mapping in the West African context. *Open Geogr. Rev.*, 126, 103782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ogrev.2020.103782>

Sawadogo, B., 2021. Cartographie des reliefs de l'ouest du Nord Burkina Faso (Afrique de l'Ouest): Implications géomorphologiques et géologiques. PhD Thesis, Université Joseph Ki-Zerbo, Ouagadougou, 276p. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-04430009/>

Vassilopoulos, P.M., Birnham, G.H., Beckler, T.A., Ranine, P.R., 1994. 40Ar/39Ar analysis of sapropelic ironite and aluminum implications to the paleoweathering history of the Western USA and West-Africa. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 58, 401-409. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7169\(94\)00473-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7169(94)00473-1)

Zachos, J.C., Dickens, G.R., Côté, F.E., 2008. An early Cenozoic perspective on greenhouse warming and carbon-cycle dynamics. *Nature* 451, 279-282. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06888>